

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF CO₂ EMISSION BETWEEN DEVELOPED AND DEVELOPING COUNTRIES

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Abstract

This paper aims to make a comparative analysis of the environmental sustainability efforts between developed and developing countries. Environment is a global product and thus every country in the world shares the responsibility of its protection from degradation. Developing countries which are transforming into industrialised developed countries are often blamed for degrading environment more compared to developed countries. The process of development is consuming lot of resources of developing countries so it is difficult for such countries to invest for environmental sustainability. Developed countries with advanced technologies and infrastructure has greater ability to address environmental issues.

Findings based on comparative analysis of CO₂ emission shows disparities in the environmental protection efforts of developed and developing countries. Developed countries are rich in resources and technological advancements but still they prefer to purchase carbon credits from developing countries rather than earning on its own. Moreover, unequal bargaining relationship between developed and developing countries have influenced the operations and policies made by international institutions. The analysis also highlights instances of innovation and efforts taken by developing countries to promote sustainable development despite resource constraints.

Key words: *CO₂ emission, environmental sustainability, resources constraints, green technology*

➤ Introduction:

Historically if one observes and study the issue of CO₂ emission, it is very much clear that developed countries has deposited more CO₂ in the atmosphere since ages as compared to developing countries who are new entrants in causing environmental degradation. Thus developed countries should put more and absolute efforts to control environmental degradation

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and reduce carbon emission. One cannot treat developed and developing countries at par in sharing the responsibility of reducing environmental degradation as carbon emission by developed countries is due to nature of lifestyle and that of developing countries is for survival and for development. Developed regions had developed themselves in the past without any hindrances of environmental policies and rules. It is therefore, Developed countries which are at the adult stage of their industrialization and now after having enough resources and developed technology to control their CO₂ emission, should lead in mitigating climate change. However, developed countries are blaming developing countries for emitting more CO₂ through their process of industrialization which is still at infant stage. Importantly, developing countries cannot go without industrialization and development, it is a pressing need for their survival. On one hand we have developed countries with advanced technology and resources to mitigate climate change caused during their process of industrialization in the past and present and on the other hand we have developing countries with resources just enough for industrialization and development and who are one having recently started emitting more CO₂ in the environment. Stockholm Declaration (2001) have also mentioned that advanced countries are financially and technically advanced enough to combat GHG emission. Also controlling GHG emission has an unwarranted social cost and will force developing countries to compromise their development goal over environmental sustainability.

One solution to control CO₂ emission is given by Kyoto Protocol through its Clean Development Mechanism (CDM) provision which has allowed Developed countries to meet their CO₂ emission targets by buying carbon credits from developing countries. Thus through their power of money, Developed countries are dumping their carbon to developing countries instead of controlling it. Developing countries as a result are reaching close to their CO₂ emission limits thereby creating hurdles in their industrialisation and development process.

Thus keeping these facts in mind, there is a need to have fair distribution of responsibility to mitigate climate change among developed and developing regions.

This paper is therefore an attempt to understand the major emitters of CO₂ at global level in the past and present, find out the amount of CO₂ emission by different regions especially developed and developing region in the world. This study will also observe different sources of CO₂ emission for some developed and developing countries. The results of this study will help to decide criteria for the fair distribution of responsibilities to mitigate climate change.

Environment being a global public good, everyone try to have free ride while exploiting its resources but no one is voluntarily taking the responsibility of its conservation. Importantly

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developed regions who exploit environmental resources pass on the negative externalities in terms of global warming, melting of glaciers etc. to those countries which are trying their hard for the protection of environment as its degradation will risk their survival.

It is therefore, various attempts have been made at the international level to combat environmental degradation. Some of them are United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) (1992), Kyoto Protocol (1997), Paris Agreement (2015), Montreal Protocol (1987), Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) (1992), Stockholm Convention on Persistent Organic Pollutants (POPs) (2001), Minamata Convention on Mercury (2013). All these agreements represent global efforts to address various environmental challenges and promote sustainable development.

➤ **Objectives:** Following are the objectives of this research paper:

1. To observe the major CO₂ emitters in the past and present
2. To compare the CO₂ emission between developed and developing regions
3. To analyse the different sources of CO₂ emissions in different countries
4. To understand the efforts taken by developed regions and by developing countries like India to mitigate climate change

➤ **Rationale:**

This study aims to find out major CO₂ emitters in the past and present so that one can fix the responsibilities to control environmental degradation in a fair manner. Efforts of mitigation based on current emission may be unjust on the part of developing regions. Lot of studies have been done on control of environmental degradation, GHG emissions. However, a comparative analysis between developed and developing regions is essential. The rationale of this paper is to contribute a better collective understanding of the drivers of CO₂ pollution and fix their responsibilities.

Observation of various sources of CO₂ emissions in different region will help to bring out solutions to control its emission and also provide inputs for environmental policies to ban or subsidies the production and consumption of goods and services.

➤ **Scope of the study:**

The major cause of global warming is GHG emission where gases other than CO₂ are more or equally degrading environment and dangerous for the human life. However, non availability of historical data on all GHG and as this study wishes to make a comparative analysis in environmental degradation of developed and developing regions in the past and present, this

paper has restricted its scope to CO₂ emission. The present study is also focusing on CO₂ emissions of countries like USA, France, China and India where USA and France are representing developed regions whereas China and India are representing developing and emerging economies.

➤ **Data collection & methodology:**

The present study has used the secondary data published by World Inequality report 2022 on CO₂ emission. World Inequality Report 2022 has published data on CO₂ emission from 1850 to 2022 for almost 80 countries.

To study global carbon emissions the current study will observe the total emission as well as per capita emission. This paper also observes the carbon emission from different sources as well as by different groups of individuals. Graphical representation of the data provides better understanding of the issue therefore this paper has used graphs and pie charts to represent data on CO₂ emission

➤ **Literature review:**

Wheeler D. (2011) in his research work titled “Fair shares: Crediting Poor countries for Carbon Mitigation” has made an extensive study of national CO₂ mitigation costs of 174 countries from 1990 to 2008. It has been observed that developing countries since 1990 have been critical participants in and have borne a fair share of global CO₂ mitigation. Author suggests that developed countries are required to invest more aggressively in low carbon energy to match CO₂ mitigation of developing countries. He claims that developed countries are required to give more of its income for the cause as they have created more than their fair share of the problem.

Another study by Gough (2011) in his paper titled “Climate change, Double Injustice and Social policy: a Case Study of the United Kingdom” on reduction of CO₂ emission efforts by UK where UK is legally committed to reduce emissions of greenhouse gases by 80 per cent by 2050, compared with the base year of 1990. Carbon mitigation policy developed by UK is highly opposed by its citizen for its regressive nature as it increases burden of low income groups.

Dinda S. and Coondoo D. (2005) have investigated the casual relationship between income and emission in their research work titled “Income and emission: A Panel Data-based Cointegration Analysis” using ECM model for their Panel data of 88 countries covering the time period 1960–1990. The results obtained suggest that there is more or less a two way causal

relationship between Per capita GDP and Per Capita CO₂ for Africa, Central America, America as a whole, Eastern Europe, Western Europe, Europe as a whole and the World as a whole.

Jaunky V. (Mar 2011) “The CO₂ Emissions-Income Nexus: Evidence from Rich Countries” has uncovered unidirectional causality running from real per capita GDP to per capita CO₂ emissions in both the short-run and the long-run. The empirical analysis based on individual countries provides evidence of an EKC for Greece, Malta, Oman, Portugal and the United Kingdom. However, it can be observed that for the whole panel, a 1% increase in GDP generates an increase of 0.68% in CO₂ emissions in the short-run and 0.22% in the long-run. The “Emission Gap Report 2022” mentioned that the world is not on track to reach the Paris agreement goals and global temperatures can reach 2.8⁰ c by the end of the century. Thus the world needs to cut GHG by 45% to avoid global catastrophe. According to this report, the growth of GHG emissions has slowed down from 2.6 % to 1.1% from the period 2000-2009 to 2010-2019. It has also been reported that 75% of GHG emissions are done by G20 members.

- **Data Analysis and Findings:** Let us first understand India’s Carbon footprint from all sectors from 1981 to 2019 with the help of following graph 1.1.

Figure 1.1: India’s Personal CO₂ Footprint (1981-2019)

Source: Databank, World Inequality Report 2022

An observation of the above graph shows that there is a rise in CO₂ emission in India over the period of years from 1980 to 2019. This rise in CO₂ emission is mainly due to industrial development, infrastructural development. Suggestions are made from developed countries that the developing countries should control the CO₂ emission by adopting decarbonising

technology or reducing polluting activities. India having limited resources for development cannot either afford to utilise such technology or postpone and control its development activities to reduce CO₂ emission.

This would be easy for developed countries with the enough resources and technology. But they instead of using green technology prefer to sell carbon credits to developing countries to meet their CO₂ emission targets set by Paris Agreement 2015. Such strategy by developed countries is likely to hamper the future growth of developing countries as their sell of carbon credits to developed regions have brought them close to the CO₂ emission limit set by Paris Agreement 2015. Thus for sustainable development of developing countries on one hand and for the control of global warming on the other, there is need to have common but differentiated responsibilities to reduce CO₂ emission by developed and developing regions. For this reason one must know the major polluters of CO₂ in 2020 at the world level.

Figure 1.2: Major Polluters of CO₂ at world level (2022)

Source: Emission Gap Report 2022

The above graph 1.2 has made an international comparison of per capita CO₂ emission by different regions. The graph clearly shows that among developed regions, USA is the major emitter of CO₂ in 2020 and that of India's CO₂ emission is lower than 3 tonnes much below

the world average CO₂ emission of 6.6 tonnes. China also seems to be among major polluters of CO₂. But it has recently added to the CO₂ deposition in the atmosphere.

Thus before fixing the responsibilities to control CO₂ emission, a comparison of historical data on CO₂ emission of different countries is essential. Thus following graph shows the data on CO₂ emission by developed and developing regions over the years from 1980 to 2020.

The following graph 1.3 shows historical and current emissions by world region. It can be clearly seen from below graph that current emission of China region is highest compared to all other regions. However, when compared with historical data, North America has been a major emitter of CO₂. When compared in relation to population, it is also clear that developing regions and least developed regions like South and South East Asia, Sub Saharan Africa, Latin America have lower CO₂ emission. Whereas North America, Russia and Central Asia, Europe are having large CO₂ emission as compared to their population size.

Figure 1.3: International comparison of Historical and Current CO₂ emission (2019)

Source: Databank, world Inequality report 2022

Carbon emission includes territorial emission as well as emission associated with import of goods and services from other countries. North American import smart phones from East Asia, carbon emission created in the production, transport and sale are attributed to North Americans. However, the authority of such regions only report territorial emissions to show their progress on emission reduction at international climate summits. Carbon credit market is used strategically by these developed countries to hide their carbon emission by dumping their carbon to developing or LDCs. Also such developed countries dump their carbon intensive industries in these countries and try to reduce their territorial emission. For e.g. Europe, Russia and Central Asia and North America data on carbon foot print is 9.7, 9.9 and 20.8 respectively whereas their territorial emission is 7.9, 11.9 and 19.8 respectively. Thus territorial emission

data may mislead and thereby these regions may not put enough efforts on climate change mitigation. It is therefore necessary to account total carbon footprint rather than territorial CO₂ emission. Thus taking into account, the emission from net import of goods and service can help in getting a fair data on per capita carbon emission.

The present study has therefore selected 4 countries i.e. USA, France, India and China where first two countries are developed countries and the latter are developing one. A comparative analysis of their National territorial emission per capita and their net import CO₂ emissions is done using line graph 1.4.

Figure 1.4: Territorial CO₂ emission of USA, France, India and China (1990 - 2020)

Source: created by the author based on Databank, World Inequality Report 2022

The above graph shows territorial emission which includes emission within the boundaries of a country excluding emissions from net imports embedded in goods and services from the rest of the world. It can be clearly seen that USA is the major pollutant of CO₂ followed by France. Although the trend after 2010 is showing a decline it is much higher than India and China. After 2010 China has overpassed the CO₂ emission of France. This is mainly due to shift of carbon intensive from developed countries to China. India is always having lowest and close to targeted CO₂ emission. USA and France be industrialised and technologically advanced countries still their territorial emission from domestic activities is very high. This is mainly due to their energy inefficient technology and reckless use of environmental resources.

Figure 1.5: Net Import of CO₂ emission by USA, France, India and China (1990 -2020)

Source: created by author based on Databank, World Inequality Report (2022)

The above graph shows the national net imports of CO₂ emission. Both developed countries USA and France are having high net import CO₂ emission. Importantly USA has the highest territorial emission but France is the largest net CO₂ importer among these four nations. While USA and many European countries have put little efforts to control their territorial emission, it is more than offset by their net imports of goods and services which are having more carbon intensive energy mix.

An insignificant fall in CO₂ emission that we observe in reports made by developed countries can be attributed to strategic carbon transfer to developing countries by transferring carbon intensive industries to developing countries, through buying carbon credits and by only reporting territorial CO₂ emission hiding their net import CO₂ emissions. This clearly shows that there are no absolute and significant efforts put by developed countries to control its CO₂ emission.

UNFCCC which reports only the territorial emission within the boundaries of the countries clearly shows developing exporting countries responsibilities to control CO₂ emission. Thus it penalises the developing countries for the emissions associated with the goods that are not consumed by them. These carbon intensive goods are produced for developed countries so in fact the major responsibilities lie with developed countries.

World inequality Report 2022, has also made an interesting finding while observing correlation between Economic inequality and Carbon inequality. Richest East Asians are emitting 39 tonnes per capita whereas Richest Europeans are emitting 29 tonnes of CO₂. This difference can

be attributed to high economic inequality in East Asia as compared to Europe. Also for less developed regions of Sub-Saharan Africa and South and South east Asia, their bottom 50% of the population are achieving the threshold target set by Paris agreement of 1.5⁰ C per capita budget. Even for regions such as Europe, Russia and Central Asia bottom 50% of the population fall within the emission limit for 2⁰ C budget. Also a global data on carbon emission depicts similar picture where bottom 50% global population emit on average 1.6 tonnes per annum and the top 10% emit 31 tonnes whereas top 1 % of global population emits 110 tonnes of carbon. Thus more than half of all emissions are contributed by rich class at the global level. It is the rich class in all these regions who are major emitters of CO₂. Therefore climate mitigation efforts should also include policies to curb the income inequalities within regions as well as at global level.

Another interesting fact highlighted by World inequality report 2022 is that the CO₂ emission reduction by lower and middle income groups of rich countries is about 15-20% of the world population, of course such reduction is not sufficient to meet the target set by Paris Climate Agreement to limit global warming to 1.5⁰ C and 2⁰ C. The top rich are polluting at much higher rate overpassing the reductions done by lower and middle income group. Introduction of carbon tax to mitigate CO₂ emission however has been strongly protested by people where the gap between rich and middle and lower income group is large and thus maximum tax burden is borne by the latter group causing further rise in economic inequality. Thus there is need to rethink of environmental policies to avoid further rise inequality.

➤ **Conclusion:**

The fundamental question of who is responsible for emission can be answered by a comparison of territorial and net import CO₂ emission of different countries. The present study has observed the CO₂ emission and its comparison at territorial and net import level for four countries. It clearly shows that developed countries like USA and France are having both production and consumption emission at high level whereas developing countries like India is having both lower production and consumption emission of CO₂.

In principle, a carbon tax can be a powerful tool to control CO₂ emission. It has also been successful in limiting carbon emission in some countries. However, French example shows that when carbon policies are improperly designed without considering socio economic structure and inequalities, such tax policy has been proven to be regressive in nature increasing further inequalities. Thus such policies can easily fail and protested by the society.

Carbon credit is another solution provided by Kyoto Protocol (CDM) to control CO₂ emissions. However, Carbon credit market can only provide short term benefits to developing countries. These countries CO₂ emission is much below the set target and thus they are selling their carbon credits to developed countries and are earning valuable foreign currencies. But this provision is detrimental for their future economic growth as they will be exhausting their potential CO₂ emission limit. Developed countries through their power of money have indirectly shifted the responsibility of climate change mitigation to developing countries by buying Carbon credit from them.

The developing countries in their quest for economic development and poverty reduction are expected to put economic development and industrialization at the forefront of their goals before giving consideration to environmental issues. Therefore, compelling developing countries like those in Sub-Saharan Africa and South Asia to pursue environmental goals, particularly reduction in CO₂ emissions, will require substantial economic, technological and financial support from developed countries and the international community to compensate for the economic losses associated with reducing pollution.

Given all the above facts, the present study provides following suggestions:

1. Governments need to track individual emissions within countries so that a more target environmental policy can be made.
2. Every country should publish their aggregate carbon footprint rather than publishing only territorial emission as such data may be misleading especially after the globalisation where it is easy to transfer carbon intensive industries to developing and LDCs.
3. The relationship between socio economic inequality and carbon inequality to be studied so that proper well acceptable environmental policies can be designed.
4. Climate policies must address inequalities within country. Indian government provides subsidies to encourage use of decarbonizing technologies and resources. For e.g. Indian government in order to reduce CO₂ emission from burning of fossil fuel has introduced schemes like Ujjwala yojana. Other schemes like Har Ghar toilet, Solar plant for decarbonisation of energy consumption by households and industries etc. are very successful in controlling CO₂ emission on a larger scale.
5. Low carbon infrastructure can make clean energy accessible and affordable to lower income groups. An eventual introduction of carbon tax then after can provide option for poor between greener and carbon emitting fossil.

6. Common Carbon tax to all may further widen the gap between rich and poor and generate distress among poor people. Such tax will be regressive as rich people will face less burden of tax and thus may emit more CO₂ and poor will be punished even if they are the insignificant emitters. A progressive Carbon tax based on level of emission or income level can help to mitigate carbon emission in more egalitarian way. Some of the progressive carbon tax suggested by Chancel and Piketty are tax on luxurious carbon emitting consumption items for e.g Air conditioners, refrigerators, Luxurious cars, Business class tickets.

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